

Complexes of α -Nitroso- β -naphthol and Properties of their Charge Transfer Bands

M A AL-QURASHI and A A M ALY*

Chemistry Department Faculty of Applied Sciences Umm Al Qura University Makkah Al Mukarramah Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Manuscript received 3 May 1993 revised 2 November 1993 accepted 12 January 1994

Four complexes of Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} comprising the ligands α -nitroso- β -naphthol, dithizone or 8-hydroxyquinoline have been prepared. The interaction of tris(naphthoquinoneoximate)iron(III), $\text{Fe}(\text{nqo})_3$, with dithizone produces a dark green compound, which shows a new band around 700 nm, assignable to a charge transfer transition between dithizone and the iron complex. A solid complex of the formula $\text{Fe}(\text{nqo})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{Dz}$ (nqo = naphthoquinoneoximate, H_2Dz = dithizone) could be isolated in a pure form. According to the Hush's theory some spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters have been calculated and the values depend on the solvent used. The electronic spectra of the following systems display charge transfer bands around 700 nm: $\text{Fe}(\text{nqo})_3/\text{dimethylglyoxime}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{HQA})_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol, $\text{Fe}(p\text{-MeHQA})_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol [HQA = 5-phenylazo-8-hydroxyquinoline, $p\text{-MeHQA}$ = 5-(*p*-methylphenylazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline]. The spectral data of these systems in different solvents and the spectroscopic and thermodynamic data of the system $\text{Fe}(\text{nqo})_3/\text{dimethylglyoxime}$ have been calculated.

Metal complexes of α -nitroso- β -naphthol are the subject matter of many investigations^{1,2} due to the importance of this ligand and its related compounds (which contain the oxime group) in photometric analysis and gravimetric determinations. Complexes of dithizone with many metals are known but reports are scarce on its mixed ligand complexes^{3,4}. The theory of metal-based mixed valence complexes (MBMV) is well documented^{5,6}. Bi- or polynuclear complexes containing the same metal in two different oxidation states are MBMV compounds, the compounds containing ruthenium in the oxidation states 2 and 3 ($\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}\text{-L-Ru}^{\text{III}}$) being typical^{6,7}. In this investigation we have discussed the interaction between the tris(naphthoquinoneoximate)iron(III) and dithizone or dimethylglyoxime as well as that of tris(5-arylazo-8-hydroxyquinolinato)iron(III) and α -nitroso- β -naphthol. The theory advanced by Hush³ provides the basis for this discussion.

Results and Discussion

Bis(naphthoquinoneoximate)nickel(II) and -Cu(II) react with dithizone to form mixed ligand complexes according to the equation

where $\text{M} = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ or Cu^{II} $\text{nqoH} = \alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol
 H_2Dz = dithizone

Bis(naphthoquinoneoximate)iron(III) reacts with dithizone to form a green solution, from which a dark green compound could be isolated. A similar complex could also be separated from the interaction of tris(8-hydroxyquinolinato)iron(III) and α -nitroso- β -naphthol its spectral data in solution has been reported⁸.

The isolated complexes (Table 1) are soluble in chloroform, acetone, alcohol, DMSO and DMF. The complexes $\text{Ni}(\text{nqo})(\text{HDz})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{nqo})(\text{HDz})$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{nqo})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{Dz}$ exhibit two π bands at 1200–1210 and 3200–3240 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{N-C}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ vibrations of the dithizone moiety respectively. Further the four complexes show two bands at 1580–1590 and 1060–1090 cm^{-1} attributed to the α -nitroso- β -naphthol moiety.

The two iron complexes exhibit moments (4.9–5.1 B.M.) that are consistent with octahedral coordination and a high-spin configuration. The diamagnetic nature of the nickel complex indicates its square-planar structure around Ni^{II} . The magnetic moment value for the copper complex (2.20 B.M.) is in fair agreement with values reported for tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes.

TABLE 1 — ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis ^o . Found/(Calcd)		
	C	H	N
Ni(nqo)(HDz)	56.39	3.89	14.92
(Dark brown)	(56.82)	(3.52)	(14.40)
Cu(nqo)(HDz)	56.61	3.62	14.58
(Black)	(56.26)	(3.48)	(14.25)
Fe(nqo) ₃ .H ₂ Dz	62.97	3.40	11.30
(Dark green)	(62.33)	(3.64)	(11.82)
Fe(8-HQ) ₃ .nqoH	65.36	3.50	7.89
(Green)	(67.19)	(3.80)	(8.46)

The thermal behaviour of two of the complexes, namely Ni(nqo)(HDz) and Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz was studied over the temperature range 50–700. For the complex Ni(nqo)(HDz) two distinct steps are observed in the TG thermogram at 216 and 480, each step corresponding to an exothermic peak in the DSC diagram. The TG thermogram of Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz shows three stages at 189, 437 and 546; the DSC diagram exhibits correspondingly three exothermic peaks.

The electronic spectra (CHCl₃) of the complexes and α -nitroso- β -naphthol and dithizone are presented in Table 2. The spectra of the complexes indicate the presence of the coordinated ligands. Thus, the dithizonate moiety exhibits a number of bands as follows: Ni(nqo)(HDz), 687, 569, 475 nm; Cu(nqo)(HDz), 445 nm; Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz, 654 nm. The band observed at 276–282 nm for all the complexes is assigned to the α -nitroso- β -naphtholate. The bands located at 754 and 758 nm for Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz and Fe(8-HQ)₃.nqoH respectively, are ascribed to charge transfer transitions. It is to be noted that the two mixed ligand

TABLE 2 — ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd	λ max nm
	(ϵ , cm ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹ dm ³)
Ni(nqo)(HDz)	687(9 000), 569(13 000), 475(15 000), 330(14 000), 285(18 000)
Cu(nqo)(HDz)	466(5 000), 445(5 900), 282(9 000)
Fe(nqo) ₃ .H ₂ Dz	754(9 000), 654(10 000), 408(14 000), 275(27 000)
Fe(8-HQ) ₃ .nqoH	758(9 000), 603(14 000), 409(42 000), 276(47 000)
nqoH	375(11 000), 282(10 000)
H ₂ Dz	614(32 000), 447(20 000)

*In CHCl₃

complexes, viz. Ni(nqo)(HDz) and Cu(nqo)(HDz) are among the stable ternary complexes of dithizone which could be isolated in the present work. In some cases the ternary complex formed is unstable and undergoes a disproportionation into the two binary complexes⁹ or a complete displacement of the coordinated ligand by dithizone may occur¹⁰. We isolated earlier a number of related complexes, e.g. Ni(ox)(HDz), ox = 8-hydroxyquinolate⁴, Ni(R₂xan)(HDz), R₂xan = alkylxanthate¹¹; Cu(alkyl-sal)(HDz), alkyl-sal = alkylsalicylaldiminate¹⁰.

The electronic spectra of Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz were recorded in different solvents, namely, acetonitrile, DMSO, DMF, ethanol, chloroform and acetone. The above assigned CT band at 754 nm is ascribed to an electron transfer transition from the highest occupied orbital of H₂Dz to the lowest unoccupied or partially occupied metal orbital. Owing to this CT character, the energy of the absorption maximum depends on the polarity of the solvent. In order to make use of the properties of this CT band, the relationship between optical and thermal electron transfer, the theory suggested by Hush⁵ is applied. Accordingly the energy of the optical transition at the absorption maximum (E_{op}) is related to the internal energy difference between two thermally equilibrated redox isomeric states (ΔE) and the re-organisational energy (χ) by the equation,

$$E_{op} = \chi + \Delta E$$

The half-width of the CT band ($\Delta \nu_{1/2}$) and the activation energy (E_{th}^*) for thermal electron transfer are given by the relations,

$$\chi = 3.606 (\Delta \nu_{1/2})^2$$

$$E_{th}^* = E_{op}^2 / 4\chi$$

χ can be expressed as the sum of a term arising from localised (metal-ligand) vibrational modes (χ_{inner}) and a term arising from lattice vibrational modes or vibrational modes of the solvent system (χ_{outer}),

$$E_{op} - \Delta E = \chi_{inner} + \chi_{outer}$$

Using dielectric continuum model, χ_{outer} is predicted to vary with $(1/D_{op} - 1/D_s)$, where D_{op} and D_s are the optical and static dielectric constants of the solvent respectively. Spectroscopic and thermodynamic data of Fe(nqo)₃.H₂Dz in different solvents are presented in Table 3. A linear relationship was obtained from plot-

TABLE 3 — SPECTROSCOPIC THERMODYNAMIC AND $(1/D_{op} - 1/D_s)$ DATA OF $Fe(nqo)_3 H_2Dz$

Solvent	E_{op} kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔE kJ mol ⁻¹	E_{th}^* kJ mol ⁻¹	χ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹	$(1/D_{op} - 1/D_s)$
Acetonitrile	169.78	86.98	87.03	82.80	3.947	0.52
Ethanol	166.89	77.40	77.80	89.50	4.142	0.50
Dimethylformamide	167.86	81.05	81.14	86.81	4.009	0.46
Dimethylsulphoxide	165.93	85.85	85.95	80.08	3.900	0.44
Acetone	161.12 ^a	—	—	—	—	—
Chloroform	159.20 ^a	—	—	—	—	—

^aBands for which $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ could not be obtained accurately

ting χ against $(1/D_{op} - 1/D_s)$ for the solvents ethanol, DMF and DMSO. This linearity may reinforce the validity of Hush theory in this case.

Mixing α -nitroso- β -naphthol solutions (2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) with solutions of 5-aryazo-8-hydroxyquinolinateiron(III) (2×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) in different solvents or upon mixing solutions of tris(naphthoquinoneoximate)iron(III) (1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) with solutions of dimethylglyoxime (1×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³) produces the same colour development, namely, a green colouration of these solutions corresponding to a new band at about 700 nm. These new bands are clearly due to an outer-sphere optical CT transition from α -nitroso- β -naphthol or dimethylglyoxime to iron(III) in the complexes. The charge transfer bands of these systems in different solvents are presented in Table 4. Some spectroscopic and thermodynamic parameters of the system $Fe(nqo)_3$ /dimethylglyoxime in DMSO are as follows: E_{op} , 166.89 kJ mol⁻¹; ΔE , 83.99 kJ mol⁻¹; E_{th}^* , 83.99 kJ mol⁻¹; χ , 82.90 kJ mol⁻¹; $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$, 3.948 cm⁻¹. The charge trans-

fer band of the system $Fe(HQA)_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Charge transfer band of the system $Fe(HQA)_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol in dimethylsulphoxide.

TABLE 4 — CHARGE TRANSFER BANDS OF THE SYSTEMS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

System	χ_{max} cm ⁻¹	Solvent
$Fe(HQA)_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol	12.285	CH ₂ Cl ₂
	13.908	EtOH
	14.144	DMSO
$Fe(p-MeHQA)_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol	13.661	CH ₃ CN
	14.880	EtOH
$Fe(nqo)_3$ /dimethylglyoxime	13.986	DMSO
	14.184	EtOH

It is to be noted that such a treatment of the CT bands in this investigation is also adopted for the ion-pair $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, PQ^{2+} (where $PQ^{2+} = 1,1'$ -dimethyl-4,4'-bpy²⁺)¹² and for the system $Fe(acac)_3/\alpha$ -nitroso- β -naphthol⁸.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grades. Dithizone and α -nitroso- β -naphthol (B. D. H.) were used

as such. Tris(naphthoquinoneoximato)iron(III)², 5-aryazo-8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives¹³ were prepared by reported methods. The iron(III) complexes of the 5-aryazo-8-quinolines were prepared according to a method similar to that of tris(8-hydroxyquinolinato)iron(III)¹⁴.

(Dithizonato)(naphthoquinoneoximato)nickel(II) and -copper(II): An equimolar (2.0 mmol) mixture of bis(naphthoquinoneoximato)nickel(II) or -copper(II) (2.0 mmol) and dithizone (2.0 mmol) both in CHCl₃ (20 ml each) was refluxed for 2 h, then the solvent evaporated by ca. 50% when the complex precipitated. The solid was washed with little cold CHCl₃ and dried.

Tris(naphthoquinoneoximato)(dithizone)iron(III): A chloroform solution (10 ml) of dithizone (2.0 mmol) was added with stirring to a chloroform solution (20 ml) of tris(naphthoquinoneoximato)iron(III) (2.0 mmol). The mixture was refluxed for 12 h, then the solution evaporated to about one-third the original volume and the resulting solid was washed with little cold CHCl₃ and dried.

Tris(8-hydroxyquinolinato)(naphthoquinoneoxime) iron(III): It was prepared in a similar manner to that of tris(naphthoquinoneoximato)(dithizone)-iron(III), except that the mixture was refluxed for 1 h.

The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 200-G spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (CHCl₃) on a Varian DMS 100S spectrophotometer. Magnetic moment was determined at room temperature by the Gouy method. The thermal measurements were carried out on a Mettler TA 3000 thermal analyser with a heating rate of 10 min⁻¹.

References

1. F. G. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", Van Nostrand, New York, 1947, Vol. III; A. JANOWSKI and J. J. CUKROWSKI, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1971, **7**, 185; S. V. PATIL and J. R. RAJU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 770.
2. S. CURRIERI and G. SIRACUSA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 650.
3. K. S. MATH and H. FREISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **41**, 1682; M. F. PERPINAN, L. BALLESTER, A. SANTOS, A. MONGE, C. RUIZVOLERO and E. G. PUEBLA, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 1523; A. A. M. ALY, M. M. KAMAL, M. S. EL-MELIGY and A. I. EL-SAID, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1987, **42**, 1447.
4. A. A. M. ALY and A. H. OSMAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **30**, 379.
5. N. S. HUSH, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **8**, 391.
6. T. J. MEYER, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 94; C. CRUZZ, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **30**, 1.
7. R. W. CALLAHAN, F. R. KEENE, T. J. MEYER and D. J. SALMON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 1064.
8. A. H. OSMAN, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1991, **128**, 479.
9. M. MORIYASU and Y. HASHIMOTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **54**, 3374.
10. A. H. OSMAN, A. S. EL-SHAHAWY and A. A. M. ALY, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1990, **127**, 396.
11. A. A. M. ALY, M. M. KAMAL, M. S. EL-MELIGY and A. I. EL-SAID, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1987, **42**, 1447.
12. J. C. CURTIS, B. P. SULLIVAN and T. J. MEYER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 3833.
13. S. TAKAMOTO, Q. FERNANDO and H. FREISER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1965, **37**, 1249.
14. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 2nd ed., Longmans, London, 1960.